

USE OF MULTIMEDIA IN ORGANIZING PRACTICAL LESSONS IN MATHEMATICS

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Abstract: This article reveals the scientific and theoretical importance of using multimedia tools in the course of general secondary education mathematics lessons.

Key words: Educational system, mathematics, multimedia tools, innovation, issue.

Today, teachers of educational institutions of the continuous education system, including general secondary schools, face new problems, that is, the task of improving the quality of mastery of the taught subject. In this regard, different methods are used in the teaching of mathematics. One of them is the use of modern information technologies. One of the important achievements of computer technologies was the creation of software tools that provide the use of multimedia components. These software tools are especially important in the organization of practical and laboratory work of the educational process.

Multimedia is a tool capable of working with visual information. The word "multimedia" is derived from the Latin word "media", which means "information carrier". Multimedia computers receive words, music, images and other data, video data and work on them. It is especially important to create an electronic guide using Internet technologies such as "Macromedia Flash", "GIF Animation", "Microsoft Front Page", "Adobe Photoshop 7.0", "3D Max", "Microsoft Power Point" in a multimedia environment. Because it is convenient to create animated, colorful, and sound images in them, and it is possible to demonstrate the solution of textual problems. A computer, video, video player, digital video camera, video projector, sound output device, video screen and microphone are used to demonstrate mathematical and physical experiments (problem solving). It is known that demonstration is important in the teaching of mathematics and natural sciences in general secondary schools. Especially in chemistry, although it is more dangerous to actually perform the explosion process (as a result of the introduction into the reaction), it is safe and convenient to show it through multimedia. Also, showing other chemical processes and the process of solving many physical problems expands the students' imagination. In physical problems, it is possible to demonstrate the phenomenon of the photoeffect, the boiling process of water, and many similar phenomena through programming.

There are many textual problems in mathematics. Concepts presented in the text are shown figuratively through animations. The givens are expressed, a mathematical model is created by setting the condition. These processes are automatically displayed on the screen. Movements appear in connection with the setting of the problem presented in the text. On the basis of the constructed mathematical model, an unknown number is determined, its solution (and actions accordingly) is shown and a solution is found. Taking this into account, we have created virtual stands for mathematics for 9th grade students. Below is an example of solving one issue of a virtual stand.

Matter. The plane started to take off from the airport. After 3 minutes, the height of the plane was determined according to the equation $h=t^2-2t-1$. How many kilometers will the plane rise after 8 minutes?

Solving. When the text of the problem is presented on the screen, the plane and its movement lane will appear. The plane starts moving on the screen and starts to climb up. Then, depending on the movement of the aircraft, an indicator direction will appear and flash, and t will appear

above the indicator, which indicates the time (minutes) spent on the traveled path. As the aircraft ascends, the upward direction indicator will also appear and blink, and h will appear above the indicator, indicating the aircraft's climb altitude (km).

When solving the problem, "h - height", "t - time" is written on the screen, and it is required to find the height of the plane h when t=8. The up pointer flashes between the plane and the plane, "h=?" appears.

Then the expansion is given: $h=t^2-2t-1$, $t=8$, $h=8^2-2*8-1=64-16-1=48-1=47$, $h=47$. "So climbed 47 km" on the screen.

Therefore, the use of multimedia environment helps the student to find a solution to the problem through practical work (visualization). It is known that seeing with the eyes is better stored in the student's memory than hearing. It is also possible to review past presentations and slides that have been shown once through multimedia. This gives an opportunity to repeatedly see the process of solving textual problems and the definition of similar concepts. Creating conditions for students to perform practical exercises based on multimedia tools led to an increase in the level of mastery of educational materials.

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